

CENTYLE BIOTECH PRIVATE LIMITED

Ward No-2, Ray Colony Transit Camp,

Rudrapur, Uttarakhand 263153

Mob: +91-8460739792 +91-7857914077

Email: centylebiotech@gmail.com Website: www.centylebiotech.com

Metagenomics 16s Report

Reported and analyzed by

Customer Name:	Prof. Naveen Kumar Navani
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Order Id:	BKMTG2314
Date of samples received	05.09.2022
No. of samples received	07
Condition of sample received	Good
Sample Name	LZ1

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Services Availed:

- **DNA Extraction**
- **DNA QC**
- **PCR amplification with V3-V4 Primers**
- **PCR Product Purification**
- **Sequencing using Illumina MiSeq Platform**
- **Data Analysis & Report Generation**

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Protocol:

DNA Extraction : (Optional)

DNA extraction is done using the suitable method for the sample type from commercially available kits such as QIAGEN, ZYMO RESEARCH, ThermoFisher

Dna extraction was done as per the manufacturer's recommendation.

PCR Amplification of V3-V4 Region of 16s Gene:

Composition of TAQ Master MIX:

- 1) High-Fidelity DNA Polymerase
- 2) 0.5mM dNTPs
- 3) 3.2mM MgCl₂
- 4) PCR Enzyme Buffer

Primer Details:

16sF:- 5' AGAGTTTGATGMTGGCTCAG3'

16sR:- 5' TTACCGCGGCMGCSGGCAC3'

Conditions Used:

40ng of Extracted DNA is used for amplification along with 10pM of each primer

Initial Denaturation: 95 degree C

25 Cycles of the following condition:

Denaturation @ 95 deg C for 15 sec, Annealing @ 60 deg C for 15 sec, Elongation @ 72 deg C for 2 mins

Final Extension at 72 deg C for 10 mins and Hold at 4 deg C.

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Overview of Sequencing Protocol:

The amplicons from each sample were purified with Ampure beads to remove unused primers and an additional 8 cycles of PCR was performed using Illumina barcoded adapters to prepare the sequencing libraries. Libraries were purified using Ampure beads and quantitated using Qubit dsDNA High Sensitivity assay kit. Sequencing was performed using Illumina Miseq with 2x300PE v3 sequencing kit.

Bioinformatics protocol:

Raw data QC is done using **FASTQC** and **MULTIQC**, followed by trimming of adapters and low quality reads by **TRIMGALORE**. The trimmed reads are further taken for processing which includes merging of paired endreads, chimeria removal and OUT abundance calculation and estimation correction – this is achieved by **QIIME / MOTHUR / KRAKEN / BRACKEN workflows**. This workflow enables highly accurate investigations at genus level.

The databases used are SILVA / GREENGENES / NCBI

Each read is classified based on % coverage and identity.

The 16S workflow will be useful in identifying pathogens in a mixed sample or understanding the composition of a microbial community.

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DNA QC :

Extracted DNA from the samples were subjected to Nano Drop and GEL Check before being taken for PCR amplification:

The Nano Drop readings of 260/280 at an ~ value of 1.8 to 2 is used to determine the DNA's quality

PCR Ampliqon QC:

The amplified 16s PCR Product is purified and subjected to GEL Check and Nanodrop QC

The Nano Drop readings of 260/280 at an ~ value of 1.8 to 2 is used to determine the DNA's quality

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Sample Details for V3-V4 amplicon region

S.No	Sample Name	No. of reads (in Million)	GC Content (%)
1	LZ1	0.2M	58.5%

FastQC (v0.11.2) and MultiQC (version 1.9):

To do quality control checks on raw sequence data coming from high throughput sequencing pipelines.

Multiqc consolidates fastqc results into single report.

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GC Content

Untrimmed Reads

Trimmed Reads

FastQC: Per Sequence GC Content

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Phylum Level – Taxonomy Plot Analysis

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Classes Level – Taxonomy Plot Analysis

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Order Level – Taxonomy Plot Analysis

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Families Level – Taxonomy Plot Analysis

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Genus Level – Taxonomy Plot Analysis

The OTU table gives an overall microbial community present in the given samples. From the generated OTU the stacked bar charts are pivoted based on taxonomic levels using Microsoft Excel 2010.

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Top 10 Enriched Genus

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Additional Documents Provided:

- 1) High Quality Images
- 2) OTU table
- 3) Comparison pdf

End of Report